

Multiphysics Simulation of CABRI Power Transients with APOLLO3®-CATHARE3 Coupling via the C3PO Platform

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ABSTRACT

The demand for high-fidelity predictive tools in nuclear safety has led to multi-physics frameworks integrating reactor physics, thermal-hydraulics, and fuel performance. CEA addresses this need by coupling simulation tools of the new generation, APOLLO3®, FLICA, CATHARE3 and ALCYONE2 through its C3PO platform. Experimental validation, however, remains challenging, as reactor-scale transients are difficult to reproduce experimentally. The CABRI reactor provides unique data through controlled RIA-type transients with strong feedback. This study applies the new APOLLO3®-CATHARE3 coupling to CABRI core transients, demonstrating more consistent integration of reactor physics and system thermal-hydraulics compared with other multi-physics tools relying on the APOLLO3®-THEDI coupling, and the legacy CATHARE2 tool in stand-alone.

Keywords: Multiphysics, C3PO, Reactivity Initiated Accident (RIA), CABRI

1. INTRODUCTION

The demand for high-fidelity predictive tools in nuclear engineering has strongly motivated the development of multiphysics simulation frameworks, where , thermal-hydraulics (TH), fuel behavior, and structural mechanics are consistently coupled. Over the past decades, major initiatives have shaped this field, establishing two guiding principles that now define multiphysics simulation: (i) coupling infrastructures that manage code-to-code communication, and (ii) application-driven workflows tailored to the relevant physics and supported by experimental evidence.

Within this international context, CEA has conducted extensive efforts to develop integrated multiphysics capabilities. Building on its previous European collaborative developments, such as the NURESAFE and NURISP projects, CEA has conducted proof-of-concept studies using new-generation codes coupled through the Collaborative Code Coupling Platform (C3PO), marking a significant step forward in integrated reactor simulations [1].The C3PO platform progressively integrates several references codes, including [2]APOLLO3® for reactor physics, FLICA4 for subchannel-scale TH, and CATHARE3 for system-scale TH, while Interfacing with simplified tools such as THEDI for 1D TH modeling, aiming to extend its applications to various reactor types and transient conditions [1], [2], [3].

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Despite this progress, a validation gap persists for fully coupled applications. Benchmarks exist for stand-alone or TH solvers, but integral experiments exercising feedbacks under well-instrumented conditions are scarce. Because full-scale accidents cannot be reproduced, research reactors provide essential validation data [4]. In this regard, the CABRI reactor may play a central role. Originally designed for RIA tests, CABRI delivers transients with prompt power excursions and strong Doppler and TH feedbacks, offering unique datasets for multi-physics validation.

This work contributes to this effort by applying the CEA multiphysics environment to CABRI transients through the C3PO-based coupling of APOLLO3® and CATHARE3. Building on previous studies with CATHARE2 and APOLLO3®/THEDI, the present approach achieves a more consistent integration of neutronics and system TH. The coupled results are compared with experimental data and contrasted with APOLLO3®/THEDI, and legacy CATHARE2 simulations, highlighting the added value of integrated multiphysics.

2. CABRI TRANSIENTS

2.1. CABRI Facility

The CABRI facility (see **Fig.1**) is a pool-type research reactor for safety studies, originally designed for RIA investigations on irradiated fuel rods. Its core consists of stainless-steel-clad UO_2 fuel rods enriched to 6 wt% ^{235}U , with a maximum steady-state power of 25 MW. Reactivity is controlled by six bundles of 23 hafnium control/safety rods. A distinctive feature is the reactivity injection system, composed of four transient assemblies, each containing 24 ^3He tubes that can be pressurized up to 15 bar and rapidly depressurized to insert reactivity. This design enables controlled and reproducible power transients [5].

2.2. Transient Scenarios

During a CABRI transient, rapid depressurization of the ^3He tubes induces a prompt reactivity insertion and sharp power excursion. The response develops in three stages: Doppler feedback from fuel and coolant heating, thermal expansion of the structures, and ^3He neutron captures in the ^3He tubes leading to the Transient Over Power (TOP) effect. This hierarchy of neutronic, and TH feedbacks has been well documented in previous CABRI studies [6].

Table 1 Representative CABRI transient cases

Case	E (MJ)	FWHM (ms)	P_{He} (bar)
R1	0.14	Undefined	0.25
R2	0.31	Undefined	0.58
R3	0.53	Undefined	0.73
D2	72.8	18.0	2.60
T2D3	226.0	9.1	11.50

To systematically validate various neutronic effects, five experimental cases were selected and grouped into three scenarios: R (reactivity insertion only), D (reactivity insertion with Doppler feedback), and T (combined Doppler and TOP effects). The corresponding test conditions are presented in **Table I** (see [6] for detailed descriptions).

3. METHODOLOGY

This study, based on the C3PO multiphysics platform, couples APOLLO3® and CATHARE3. The following subsections provide a brief introduction to the C3PO coupling framework and to the single-physics models of APOLLO3® and CATHARE3 used in this work.

3.1. C3PO Coupling Platform

The C3PO platform is an open-source Python environment developed at CEA for standardized multiphysics coupling based on the ICoCo (Interface for Code Coupling) norm [7] and the SALOME MEDCoupling [8] library for field exchanges. It provides a generic framework for coupling scripts, allowing flexible integration of different solvers with minimal code modifications [2], [9]. The overall coupling philosophy is depicted in **Figure 2**, which illustrates the ICoCo interface (*left*) and mesh mapping (*right*).

Figure 1 Coupling philosophy of the C3PO platform: ICoCo API (*left*) and mesh mapping (*right*).

C3PO has three main features: (i) the ICoCo norm for standardized solver communication, (ii) the MED format for consistent exchange of mesh and field data, and (iii) a time-management module that synchronizes solvers while allowing each to advance with its own stability constraints.

3.2. Previous Multiphysics Studies on CABRI transient

Three levels of multiphysics integration are considered in this study. (i) The PALANTIR framework (CATHARE2) modeled the entire CABRI circuit with point-kinetics neutronics [6]. (ii) The APOLLO3/THEDI coupling [10], [11], introduced 3D neutronics but applied simplified core feedback, with circuit and depressurization record from PALANTIR. (iii) The present work advances to APOLLO3/CATHARE3 coupling, where full 3D neutronics are consistently linked with the system-scale CABRI loop, including the depressurization circuit. A summary of these approaches is provided in **Table II**.

Table 2 Comparison of multiphysics integration strategies for CABRI simulations: legacy and current

Level	Core (Neutronics)	Core (TH)	Depressurization Loop
(i) [6]	Point kinetics	1D TH (<i>assembly-scale</i>)	Full system representation

(ii) [11]	3D core (SP ₃)	1D thermal (<i>pin</i>) + hydraulics (<i>assembly</i>)	Boundary condition from (i)
(iii) [This study]	3D core (SP ₃)	1D assembly-scale TH (<i>with ongoing extension to 3D pin-scale</i>)	Full system representation

3.3. Main feature of the APOLLO3®/CATHARE3 coupling

This section outlines the key components of the coupled framework. **Figure 3** illustrates the APOLLO3® solver configuration (*left*) and the CATHARE3 nodalization of the CABRI system (*right*).

Figure 2 APOLLO3® core mesh configuration (*left*) and CATHARE3 system nodalization [12] (*right*).

- **APOLLO3®.** Neutronics are computed with a two-step scheme [11]. Lattice calculations produce multi-parameterized outputs (MPOs) from JEFF3.1.1 data. These output are homogenized cross sections tabulated against fuel temperature, coolant density/temperature, ³He density, and control rod state. They are the inputs of the full-core simulations using the MINOS SP₃ solver [13].
- **CATHARE3.** The CABRI system is represented in the PALANTIR model, originally based on CATHARE2 [5]. It integrates both the core circuit and the transient rods circuit, whose depressurization drives the reactivity insertion (highlighted in **Fig. 3**).
- **Coupling strategy.** The APOLLO3®/CATHARE3 coupling is implemented on the C3PO platform with a loose partitioned scheme. Steady state is obtained by fixed-point iterations, while transients are solved explicitly in a Gauss–Seidel sequence: APOLLO3® supplies the space- and time-dependent power, and CATHARE3 returns the TH feedback (fuel and coolant temperatures and coolant density) together with the helium density as in **Figure 4**.

Figure 3 APOLLO3®/CATHARE3 coupling workflow: steady-state and transient explicit exchange.

4. RESULTS

1) Steady-State Calculations

The APOLLO3®/CATHARE3 model was first verified at steady state by comparison with the reference APOLLO3®/THEDI model under identical 25 MW conditions.

Figure 4 (a) Convergence behavior of fixed point iterations for APOLLO3®/THEDI and APOLLO3®/CATHARE3 at 25 MW steady state. (b) Code to code comparison of k_{eff} and maximum fuel temperature as functions of the initial ³He pressure, under fixed water loop flow conditions.

Figure 5 summarizes two key results of this coupling verification. In **Figure 5a**, the convergence behavior of fixed point iterations is compared between APOLLO3®/THEDI and APOLLO3®/CATHARE3. The normalized error shown in **Figure 5a** is computed as the relative difference between successive iterations, defined as $\epsilon_n = \|x_n - x_{n-1}\|/\|x_{n-1}\|$, where x_n is the vector of physical quantities (specifically, fuel temperature, coolant temperature, coolant density) at iteration n . While APOLLO3®/THEDI converges within 20 iterations to the prescribed tolerance of 10⁻⁵, APOLLO3®/CATHARE3 requires substantially more iterations (around 90) due to the increased coupling complexity introduced by the full system model in CATHARE3.

A quantitative code-to-code comparison was performed at steady state, with the reactor operating at 25MW and the Initial ³He pressure varied under fixed water loop flow conditions. For each converged case, the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} and maximum fuel temperature were compared in **Figure 5b**. As expected, increasing the ³He pressure (and thus absorber density) results in a lower k_{eff} , which in turn leads to a more centrally peaked power distribution, raising the maximum fuel temperature.

The results show good agreement between the two models: the difference in k_{eff} remains within 100 pcm, and the maximum fuel temperature shows consistent trends. The use of a pin-scale thermal mesh in APOLLO3®/THEDI yields higher peak temperatures compared to the assembly-scale mesh used in APOLLO3®/CATHARE3, where the temperature field is spatially averaged over each assembly slice.

2) Transient Calculations

Subsequently, five transient scenarios at different energy scales (**Table I**) were simulated. Results were compared quantitatively with PALANTIR, APOLLO3®/THEDI, and the experiments using power-shape metrics including peak power, time-to-peak, deposited energy, and full width at half maximum (FWHM). For the low-energy R cases, APOLLO3® standalone kinetics were also included as a reference.

- **low-energy R cases** (*reactivity insertion*)

The power and reactivity over time for the R2 case are shown in **Figure 6**. The rapid depressurization of the transient assemblies increases reactivity, which in turn drives a corresponding rise in reactor power. Both the APOLLO3®/THEDI and APOLLO3®/CATHARE3 couplings predict slightly lower values than the APOLLO3® stand-alone calculation due to Doppler feedback. Due to the use of a different reactor physics model, PALANTIR exhibited different reactivity trends over time, resulting in a slight underestimation of the power variation. Among the coupled approaches, APOLLO3®/CATHARE3 shows the most pronounced improvement, achieving closer agreement with the experimental data than APOLLO3®/THEDI. The corresponding qualitative comparisons across all R cases are shown in **Table 3**.

Figure 6 Time evolution of power and reactivity: simulation results vs. experimental data (R3).

Table 3 Relative deviations $(C-E)/E$ [%] of deposited energy during the power transition (R cases).

	E Deposit		
	PALANTIR(CATHARE2)	APOLLO3/THEDI	APOLLO3®/CATHARE3
R1	5.2	4.6	4.4
R2	2.5	2.6	1.5
R3	6.8	8.4	6.2

○ **mid-energy D case** (reactivity insertion + doppler effect)

The D2 case with larger energy deposition is shown in **Figure 7**.

Figure 7 Time evolution of power and reactivity: simulation results vs. experimental data (D2).

Strong feedback effects cause the reactivity to decrease around 0.07 s, while the power peaks near 0.09s. PALANTIR and APOLLO3® CATHARE3, which simulate both the depressurization loop and the core, show better agreement with the experiment than APOLLO3®/THEDI. While their peak power

values differ slightly, APOLLO3®/CATHARE3 reproduces the timing most accurately. APOLLO3®/THEDI shows about 50% error in peak power, compared with about 27-28% for PALANTIR and APOLLO3®/CATHARE3. This difference may arise from the full system modeling in PALANTIR and APOLLO3®/CATHARE3, which capture local helium pressure variations, unlike APOLLO3/THEDI that implements the helium pressure as a boundary condition.

- **high-energy T case** (*reactivity insertion + doppler effect + TOP effect*)

The T2D3 case with higher energy deposition is shown in **Figure 8**.

Figure 8 Time evolution of power and reactivity: simulation results vs. experimental data (T2D3).

All three approaches reproduce the power peak timing within approximately 4% error and the peak power within about 20%. APOLLO3®/THEDI shows around 23% error in the peak power, compared with roughly 13% for PALANTIR and 9% for APOLLO3®/CATHARE3. The timing of the peak shows minor differences between APOLLO3®/THEDI and both PALANTIR and APOLLO3®/CATHARE3, similar to the behavior observed in the D2 case for similar reasons. APOLLO3®/CATHARE3 exhibits a deviation of about 4%, while PALANTIR shows a slightly smaller delay of around 2%. Although these differences remain small, their origin is currently under investigation.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study used the C3PO multiphysics platform to simulate CABRI reactor transients by consistently coupling APOLLO3® neutronics with CATHARE3 system TH. This approach was benchmarked against PALANTIR, which uses a point-kinetics model with a simplified 1D TH modeling, and APOLLO3®/THEDI, which couples 3D neutronics with 1D feedback under imposed boundary conditions.

The results demonstrate the complementary advantages of 3D core neutronics modeling and full system representation. In the R cases, except for PALANTIR, the results obtained from APOLLO3® standalone, APOLLO3®/CATHARE3, and APOLLO3®/THEDI were consistent, while PALANTIR exhibited a slightly different trend due to its use of a different reactor-physics model.

For the D2 case, APOLLO3®/CATHARE3 reproduced experimental trends more accurately than APOLLO3®/THEDI, both in peak timing and peak power, while remaining comparable to PALANTIR. In the T2D3 case, all methods predicted the power-peak timing within approximately 4% and the peak-power amplitude within about 20%. APOLLO3®/THEDI showed an error of around 23% in the peak power, compared with roughly 13% for PALANTIR and 9% for APOLLO3®/CATHARE3. The deviation in

peak-power timing was also similar to that observed in the D2 case, which may be attributed to whether or not the local helium pressure distribution was considered in the modeling. These findings confirm the added value of combining high-fidelity 3D neutronics and full system modeling, while further improvements are expected by extending the 1D thermal-hydraulic core model to a 3D pin-scale feedback approach.

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